

Climateurope2

Milestone

Website, visual identity and social media operative

Authors: Mauro Buonocore (CMCC), Marta Terrado (BSC), Arianna Acierno (CMCC)

Internal reviewer: Artiza Elosegi (webLyzard technology)

Funded by
the European Union

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101056933. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

The website, visual identity and animation of social media channels were among the first activities implemented under the Climateurope2 project.

The timely operationalisation of these activities enabled the project to implement the inherited tools, contacts, network database, and social media channels from the previous Climateurope project, which ended in 2021, and activate all partners regarding the flow of communication to external audiences.

The visual identity produced by BSC was the graphic basis for the creation of the website, the draft of which was presented at the Kick-off Meeting of the project that took place in Lecce, Italy, at the CMCC headquarters on September 27 and 28. Since this event, the website has gone online as well as the social media accounts - Twitter account and LinkedIn group - have been updated from the previous versions, which referred to the project's new visual identity. In addition, a new LinkedIn public page and a new YouTube channel have been created.

• Visual Identity

The visual identity of Climateurope2 was designed and created by BSC.

The logo for Climateurope2 features the word "Climateurope" in a bold, blue, sans-serif font, followed by the number "2" in a larger, yellow, sans-serif font. The entire logo is set against a white background with a thin horizontal line below it.

Fig. 1 - The Climateurope2 logo

The description of the logo, the choice of colours, and all the information necessary for the correct application of the logo in its different declinations are included in the Brand Guidelines, a manual for the use of the logo that is available to all partners in the project wiki.

The design of the Climateurope2 logo is based on the lettering of the name of the project that aims to create a modern look for the project, something relatable to the public.

Inspired by gradients referring to the graphs used to represent climate data, colour is used as an element to create a vibrant personality for the project. While the colour palette plays around the Earth, colours do not get too redundant in the ecosystem of projects.

Fig. 2 - Examples of application on different backgrounds of the Climateurope2 logo

The principal font on the branding is Lato. This font can be found on the google-fonts webpage. This ensures the correct display on the web pages and different applications.

The accent typography is MADE Kenfolg, a serif typeface that will be used for titles and headers whenever the user sees it fit.

Once the logo was designed, its applications and colour palette defined, the different declinations were produced for the application on communication materials such as slides for oral presentations and posters.

#232120	#0034BE	#ACE2C3
#8E8E8E	#0E76B8	#DDF2BF
#CECECC	#649CC5	#FFF2B1

Fig. 3 - Climateurope2 visual identity: the colour palette.

Fig.5 - Climateurope2 visual identity: the poster presentation template

● Website

The project website is a digital environment where all public information about Climateurope2 activities is made available.

Since October 2022 (M2), the site has been online, accessible at the URL www.climateurope2.eu. The website was created by BSC.

It was important to have an operational website at an early stage of the project. The online presence provides visibility for Climateurope2, gives consistency to the project identity and provides a place to reach for all relevant information on activities and to get in touch with the team.

The website should be understood as a dynamic and constantly evolving environment, a space that changes as the project activities grow and is adapted to provide the best visibility for the different activities.

In its start-up version, the website is organised into four sections plus the homepage. Additional sections will be added later on, when suitable materials are available, including a section on Guidelines and Standards as well as a Resources section.

Homepage

The homepage is designed to highlight the vision and the mission of the project and the latest information and content that shed light on the most relevant activities and outcomes related to Climateurope2.

The navigation menu gives access to all sections of the site, while scrolling down the page, one has immediate evidence of the project objectives summarised in three key concepts: Standardising, Supporting, and Increasing uptake.

One section of the homepage is dedicated to highlighting the latest publications regarding events and news. The next section offers a space for the participatory platform that will be set up during the course

of the project, while the final section is dedicated to a call to join the Climateurope2 network, with a direct link to the registration form. The contents of the homepage will be enriched with updated and fresh material that the project wishes to highlight as it advances and completes its activities (events, newsletters, deliverables, outcomes, etc.).

Fig. 5 - Climateurope2 website homepage

About us

The first menu item is dedicated to an in-depth description of the project. The section is divided into 4 subsections:

- **About the project**, presents a general description of the project and reference to the former Climateurope project;
- **Objectives**, includes a detailed outline of the results the project intends to pursue;
- **Consortium**, illustrates the geographical dimension of the partnership represented by the project with a map and the logos of the partners with links to their respective sites;
- **Projects and initiatives**, describes how the project will establish synergies and make use of knowledge from a large number of previous and current projects, initiatives, networks and international programmes, including relevant sister projects within the Horizon Europe Programme.

News and Events

The *News and Events* section is the most dynamic area of the website: it collects updates on activities and events such as webinars, workshops, conferences, etc. This section will be populated as Climateurope2 activities develop during the project; it is intended to keep track of all the initiatives related to the project or in which the project is involved.

Climateurope2 organises and participates in a number of festivals, webstivals, conferences and other events aimed at the climate services community and wider audiences. On the page dedicated to *Events*, the users will find more information about the project's upcoming and past events, as well as relevant climate services events.

Platform

A specific section is dedicated to the Climateurope2 platform. It is a digital environment that is aimed to ensure that capacity-building materials are widely available, easy to find, and usable during and after the project's lifetime. The platform also has a community engagement component that allows audiences to reach a consensus on the topics tackled by the project.

Contact

A section is also dedicated to those who would like to get directly in touch with the project team. In this regard, a form is available to be filled out to request information from the coordination team.

Finally, the footer, present on all pages of the website, is the space for institutional service sections such as the EU emblem, the acknowledgement of the funding programme and disclaimer, the Privacy Policy, Legal Notice, a button to subscribe to the newsletter and quick links to social media.

● Social media

Climateurope2's social media activities take place on three platforms:

- Twitter - <https://twitter.com/climateurope2> - with 2,321 followers
- LinkedIn:
 - 🔗 a public project page (<https://www.linkedin.com/company/climateurope2/>) with 80 followers, and
 - 🔗 a group page (<https://www.linkedin.com/groups/8573540/>) with 313 members
- YouTube channel - <https://www.youtube.com/@climateurope2609>

Data on followers and members refer to December 2022.

These accounts are managed and animated by LGI in cooperation with all partners. The Twitter account and LinkedIn group were not born from scratch but take up the activities and network of the Climateurope project with a renewed visual identity and a renewed impetus that is inspired by the new activities that are developed within Climateurope2.

KPIs are reported monthly.

Fig. 6 - Climateurope2 Youtube channel page - the video of the first webinar is the first video published on the channel

Fig. 7 - Climateurope2 LinkedIn page

Fig. 8 - Climateurope2 Twitter account